

PERCEIVED LEARNING DIFFICULTIES IN MATHEMATICS: A GENERAL QUALITATIVE RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

This general qualitative research explored the perceived learning difficulties of the learners in both junior and senior high school in mathematics-by-mathematics teachers in Marikit Normal School in the division of Marikina City. Eleven mathematics teachers from junior high school and senior high school who taught mathematics subject in previous school year 2023-2024 were participants to this study. A validated researcher-made survey questionnaire was administered to determine the perceived learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics subjects. Data collection was done through the messenger media platform with the use of google form. Results show the perceived learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics are: the mathematical learning difficulties, less mastered learning competencies, and poor mathematical skills. For mathematical learning difficulties, the researcher found out that learners have difficulty to perform the fundamental operations, difficulty to comprehend mathematical problems both numerical and word problems, and difficulty in dealing fractions. While in less mastered learning competencies, the topics on operations on rational numbers, factoring, analysis and problem solving, trigonometric identities, and statistical software are not mastered by the learners. And for the numeracy skills specifically problem-solving skills, numerical ability, and data analysis skill are the mathematical skills that need to be mastered by learners. The result of the study suggests that the findings should be considered and be the bases for the development and enhancement of some school programs for the improvement of the learners like the modification of the learning competencies of mathematics, providing more activities in problem solving, and enough time to the do activities for each grade level. Based on the findings of this study, it is also

highly recommended by the researcher to conduct further research on the factors that cause the mathematical learning difficulties of the learners.

Keywords: *Mathematical learning difficulties, Less mastered learning competencies, Poor mathematical skills*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is essential for understanding and solving problems in our technologically advanced world. Mathematics plays an essential role in the modern world across various disciplines. Specifically, this subject is significant to various fields like Technology and Innovation, Business and Finance, Science and Engineering, Healthcare and Medicine, Environmental Studies, Communication and Networking, Transportation and Logistics and Cartography etc. Without Mathematics, all of these disciplines would not be successful and there will be no development of technology and society and the world as whole.

Hodaňová and Nocar (2016) had mentioned that Mathematics is important for life and supports all-round personal development. Mathematics significantly influence students' education both in a special branch (mathematical knowledge) and in terms of moral education. They had also mentioned that in this contemporary life people should be required to have a good mathematical knowledge.

But the problem is how we can achieve these goals if there are problems facing education. Learning in some countries, especially the underdeveloped and developing countries, is in crisis. The latest result of PISA revealed a shocking low performance of most learners across the countries that participated in the global assessment, especially in Mathematics. Between 2018 and 2022, mean performance in Mathematics across Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries fell by a record 15 points (OECD 2023).

Globally, six out of ten children and adolescents are not learning a minimum in reading and mathematics, according to new estimates from the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS). The total – 617 million – includes more than 387 million children of primary school age and 230 million adolescents of lower secondary school age. This means that more than one-half – 56% – of all children won't achieve minimum proficiency levels by the time they should be completing primary education. The proportion is even higher for adolescents at 61% (UNESCO 2017).

In the study conducted by Murtiyasa and Lahtifa (2023) they have mentioned that learners had difficulty in learning mathematics because they cannot understand the material given within a certain time. Students feel bored and do not focus on understanding the material given by the teacher during distance learning. Students experienced learning difficulties in Mathematics due to lack of support from their teachers as most teachers had negative

attitude towards them. Teachers' use of poor Mathematics Instruction techniques caused the learners to have difficulties in the subject (Mitumba & Chirwa, 2024). The students' perception of the learning of mathematics greatly affects students' motivation to engage in learning mathematics and achievement. The positive perception of students encourages them for effective learning (Khanal, 2022).

The use of multimedia in teaching not just for instruction but also for students' comfort and learning is necessary and infusing humor in the videos give a new branding of the multimedia for instruction (Murillo & Tan, 2022). The development of innovative learning approaches like Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) is important as a tool to improve the learner's less mastered learning competencies in Mathematics (Lacson & Jaminal, 2024). The use of micro-lectures via ED Puzzle in delivering the lessons in Mathematics during an asynchronous online class is necessary to improve students' achievement of its learning competencies (Romorosa, 2023).

The development of student's problem solving skills is important and to create meaningful learning in mathematics that can develop complex thinking skills especially in the ability to solve problems in the field of Mathematics (Fauzi et al, 2023). The mathematical literacy skills of senior high school students in solving problems involving the system of linear equations of three variables must be developed (Melisa & Utami, 2023). Mathematical Skills must be given consideration and attention because it is significantly correlated to Mathematics Performance of the learners (Jade and Oco, 2023).

In Philippines, there is also a major learning crisis in basic education both elementary and secondary especially in Mathematics. The latest results of PISA and TIMMS revealed that there is major crisis in the basic education in the Philippines. The Philippines scored 297 in Mathematics and 249 in science, according to the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) 2019 by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA).

The country has also a dismal performance in PISA. In the latest PISA result, Philippines, once again had ended up among the countries that produced the lowest proficiency for 15-year-old students in reading, mathematics, and science as indicated by the PISA rankings. The country ranked 77th out of 81 countries globally (Magsambol, 2024).

In the local level, students from the National Capital Region have achieved an average score of Proficiency level 1 in Mathematics literacy based on the PISA 2018 (TEACHERPH). At Level 1 students can answer questions that involve familiar contexts where all of the relevant information is present, and the questions are clearly defined. They can identify information and to carry out routine procedures according to direct instructions in explicit situations. They can perform actions that are obvious and follow immediately from the given stimuli.

The Philippines is in critical situation in terms of education especially in Mathematics that requires immediate actions. The government in collaboration with some experts and researchers should do something to address this crisis in education. Now, to be able to help solve the problem, the researcher has thought of conducting a qualitative study which is, "Perceived Learning Difficulties of Senior High School Learners in Mathematics".

Initially, the first step the researcher has come up towards solving this crisis in Philippine education most especially in mathematics is to determine the specific learning difficulties of the learners. Determining learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics is crucial for effective education. It is also essential to recognize Mathematical Learning Difficulties (MLD) early to provide specific solutions and timely support to the learners.

Mathematical Learning Difficulties (MLD), also known as dyscalculia affects a person's ability to comprehend numbers, symbols, and perform mathematical calculations. Learning difficulties can significantly impact students in various ways, one of them is the poor academic performance. Students with mathematical difficulties (MD) reported lower enjoyment, lower hope, and higher anxiety than those without MD where hope and enjoyment played a mediating role between learning difficulties (LD) and academic achievement in both the literacy and math domains (Sainio et al, 2019). Students with learning difficulties may struggle to keep up with their peers academically that will lead to frustration, low self-esteem, and lack of confidence in their abilities. This struggle of the learners leads to have an education crisis of the country especially in Philippines.

While there have been actions and research to address this problem within the learners and in the education crisis of the country, there is a need for more studies that will give solution to these emerging problems that are deteriorating the quality of education.

The purpose of the study is to assess the learning difficulties of the learners in Mathematics, determine the less mastered learning competencies in Mathematics, and assess the Mathematical skills of the learners for the development of a certain solution to low performance of the learners in the local, national and global assessments.

Research Questions

The study aimed to describe the perceived mathematical learning difficulties of the junior and senior high school learners in Marikina High School in the division of Marikina City. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the learning difficulties of the learners did you observe in the mathematics subject you were teaching?
2. What are the less mastered learning competencies in the mathematics subject you were teaching?
3. What are the less mastered skills of the learners in the mathematics subject you were teaching?

METHODOLOGY

The procedures conducted in this study are described in detail such as the research design, the mechanism for the selection of the participants and the sampling procedure, the instruments, data collection, data analysis framework, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study aims to find out and describe the mathematical learning difficulties of the junior and senior high school learners in Marikit Normal School in the division of Marikina City. This research had employed a qualitative research design for the data gathering and analysis. Qualitative research is used in this study for this study focused on the perceptions and experiences of the teachers on the learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics subject.

Sampling Procedure and Participants

In this study, the non-probability sampling method which is a convenience purposive sampling was employed to choose the participants of this study. The participants of this study were all active mathematics teachers from junior high school and senior high school that taught mathematics subject in previous school year 2023-2024. They were the mathematics teachers that willingly participated in this study and they were provided with an informed consent. The chosen participants of this research were eleven (11) Mathematics teachers from junior and Senior high school of Marikit Normal School.

Table 1. Respondents as to their grade level

Grade level	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Grade 7	2	18.18
Grade 8	3	27.27
Grade 9	1	9.09
Grade 10	1	9.09
SHS	4	36.36
Total	11	100

Instruments

The researcher had formulated a survey questionnaire and undergone the process of validation. The questionnaire was divided into two parts. Part one, consists of the demographic profile of the respondents. In the demographic profile, the participants are asked to give their name, email address, school, and subject taught. While part two, consists of three open-ended questions asking the respondents on their experiences and observations on the learning difficulties of students in Mathematics subject they were teaching.

Data Collection

The following procedures were adapted by the researcher to gather the needed data for this study: First, a letter of permission to conduct the study was submitted to the school principal. Second, an informed consent for some clarifications and full information about the research was also presented to the school principal and given to the participants of this study. Third, the survey questionnaire was sent to the respondents through

messenger with the use of the google form. Fourth, the responses of the participants were retrieved and reviewed from the dashboard of the google form. When all participants had finished answering the survey, the data and all responses were reviewed through the dashboard where all responses were automatically recorded. Finally after the survey was conducted, the results were organized and analyzed thematically.

Table 2. Timeframe for collection of data

	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5
Seek permission from the school head.	June 17-22, 2024				
Present informed consent to the school head and participants					
Distribution of survey questionnaire through google form.		June 24-29, 2024			
Retrieval and review of data and responses of participants.			July 1-6, 2024		
Organization and interpretation of the data.				July 8-13, 2024	July 15-17, 2024

The Table 2 presents the time frame of the collection of the data from the first week of the procedure when researcher sought for the permission from the principal up to the last week of the procedure which was the organization and interpretation of the data.

Data Analysis Framework

Since this study is a qualitative research, the researcher had employed a framework analysis which is a thematic approach that is appropriate for this study. After the data had collected, the researcher familiarized and analyzed the data before coding them. Then the researcher had created the initial codes of the collected data. After the creation of the initial codes, the data were organized and classified into categories. After grouping the codes into categories, the data were reviewed and clustered into themes.

Nicolas (2021) defines thematic analysis as one of the most important types of analysis used for qualitative data. According to him when researchers have to analyze audio or video transcripts, they give preference to thematic analysis.

Ethical Considerations

In this study, some ethical considerations were observed. The researcher had sought permission from the school head and Mathematics department head. An informed consent was also obtained from the participants for their awareness of the purpose, procedures, risks, benefits of the study together with their rights to withdraw anytime they want. The names and the responses of the respondents were kept confidential. For confidentiality of the name of the school a pseudonym was used which is Marikit Normal School.

RESULTS

Table 3. Summary of themes

Code	Categories	Theme	Description of Themes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some students do not know the basic Math Basic operations Fundamental operations(integers), fractions, linear inequalities Mathematical operations Basic skills are not mastered can't formulate any formula. 	Fundamental Operations	Theme One: Learning Difficulties of the Learners	These themes in general are the observed learning difficulties of students in Mathematics subjects.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The comprehension capability of students No mastery of lesson Learners find it difficult to understand the topics 	Comprehension		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weaknesses in fractions Operation of signed numbers, division/fraction Lack of resources and tools that support effective teaching 	Fraction		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fundamental Operations on Integers and rational numbers Integers, fractions& linear inequality All topics under Rational 	Operations on Rational Number	Theme Two: Less mastered	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplifying Polynomials/Factoring Polynomials • Factoring 	Factoring	Learning Competencies
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The melcs which involve analysis and problem solving • Solves problems involving logarithmic functions, equations, and inequalities. 	Analysis and problem solving	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The 4th quarter MELCS • Problems involving proving trigonometric identities 	Trigonometric Identities	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operations on subtraction, Multiplication and Division 	Fundamental Operations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of Statistical Software and Technology 	Statistical Software	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Problem solving • Problem Solving • In problem solving, they cannot can't formulate the equations • Solving problems and graphing functions • Some learners very poor foundation in fractions (Rational) especially in problem solving • Solve real-world problems 	Problem-solving	Theme Three: Less mastered skills of the learners
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simplifying Polynomials/Factoring Polynomials • Integers, fractions, linear inequalities • Integers and Algebra • Rational 	Numerical Ability	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding and implementing various probability distributions 	Data Analysis	

Table 3 presents the results of the study through step-by-step process from initial coding of the data to creating categories of the data and to thematization of the data. It is shown in this table that there are three themes created such as: Theme one (1), Learning

Difficulties of the Learners in mathematics; Theme two (2), Less Mastered Learning Competencies in mathematics; and Theme three (3), Less Mastered Skills of the Learners in mathematics.

DISCUSSION

Learning Difficulties of the Learners

The Learning Difficulties of the Learners in mathematics are the struggles of the learners to cope up and master the lessons that their teachers had taught them. Some of these struggles experienced by the learners based on the responses of the participants are the following: the difficulties of the learners to perform the four fundamental operations, difficulties to comprehend some mathematical problems, and difficulties to familiarize fraction and perform the operations on this concept. Obviously, based on the data most of the learners have poor foundation in mathematics especially in fundamental operations which is very vital in learning mathematics. Once the learners had not mastered these fundamental operations all topics will be affected and this will be one of the causes of the struggles of the learners in mathematics. Proper training in basic mathematical operations through the activity-based strategies, the learners' performance in mathematics will be enhanced. When they become thorough in basic mathematical operations, they themselves get ready to do more complex operations in mathematics (Kavitha & Saravanakumar, 2014). The learning difficulties of the learners that were mentioned by the participants have an indication that the learners had not learned these topics from their previous teachers. These learning difficulties of the learners that were observed by mathematics teachers in their classes are not developed in them. These are the skills that teachers should be given focus or interventions. Mathematics teachers has to provide activities that would help learners overcome these learning difficulties in mathematics and provide students an opportunity to showcase their skills in mathematics to improve their academic performance. Giving praise at the appropriate time and providing opportunities for students to showcase their abilities in the classroom helps learners enhance mathematics learning (Khanal, 2022).

Less Mastered Learning Competencies

The Less Mastered Learning Competencies in mathematics are the topics that are not mastered by the learners such as operations on rational number, factoring, analysis and problem solving involving functions, trigonometric identities, fundamental operations, and statistical software. The data says it all, that most of the learners has really a poor foundation in mathematics. These topics in mathematics that are not mastered by the learners require a good foundation in basic concepts of mathematics like fundamental operations and fractions. The basic foundation of the learners in mathematics should be fully developed for them to connect to the new level of foundations in mathematics subjects. Mathematics is one but its foundations are many and the older foundations allow for reconstruction of a new foundations in mathematics (Rodin, 2023). The topics that are

not mastered by learners are the basic concepts in each level of mathematics subjects. So, the learning competencies for these topics should be reviewed and modified and intervention programs should be implemented also to address this problem. Strategic Intervention Material should be adopted by high school teachers as an additional learning material to address the weaknesses of the learners along the identified least learned competencies (Laña, 2023).

Less mastered skills

Least mastered skills of the learners in mathematics are the mathematical skills that are not mastered by the learners such as problem-solving skill, numerical ability, and data analysis skill. Based on the data provided by the participants, this means that most of the learners are poor in these skills which are generally connected to numeracy skill. Numeracy skill is vital foundation in mathematics and in the academic foundation of the learners that must be developed in the learners at an early age. Early math has a strong impact on later academic achievement, especially math success (Tiedeman, 2019). The results imply that something must be done to address this problem within the learners. Since numeracy skills need more activities to be practiced, the school should provide more activities and enough time to develop their numeracy skills. Additional session time is needed to provide sufficient time to deliver the lessons, and students need other activities on word problems to practice their problem-solving skills (Decena, 2021).

Overall, there is a need for continued research on identifying some factors that causes these perceived learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics that affect their academic performance, as this has important implications on the learner's ability that could be the bases of the actions of school head and mathematics teachers to address the poor performances of the learners not just in Mathematics but in all subject areas. Factors causing the learning difficulties of the learners should be identified if it is a family factor, system factor, leadership factor, teacher's factor, and etc. These factors that affect the learner's ability must be identified and confirmed to make an appropriate solution and immediate actions to the identified mathematical learning difficulties of the learners in this study.

Conclusions

The purpose of this study is to describe the perceived mathematical learning difficulties of the learners both junior and senior high school in Marikit Normal School in the division of Marikina City. The study had aimed to attain the following objectives: describe the learning abilities of the learners, determine the less mastered learning competencies in mathematics, and describe the mathematical skills of the learners. The findings of this study are a big help to address the problems perceived by teachers within their learners like the learning difficulties of the learners. Through these findings, the struggles of the learners most especially in the fundamental operations will be given focus and interventions. Likewise with less mastered learning competencies, the topics under these competencies will be revisited and reviewed. Through the findings of this study, the

teachers could have now an insight on how to improve the mastery of the learners by consistently providing an intervention activities and giving more additional materials to the learners. And so with the less mastered skills of the learners in mathematics. The findings of this study are a big help for teachers to think of activities and remedies in developing the numeracy skills of the learners like an additional session time and activities on word problems. An additional session time that will be needed to provide sufficient time in delivering the lessons and to give more activities on word problems to practice their problem-solving skills.

After a review and thorough analysis on the data and all responses of the participants in this study, the results for the learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics, less mastered learning competencies in mathematics, and less mastered skills in mathematics are as follows:

For the learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics, the researcher found out that the struggles of the learners in mathematics subject are difficulty in performing fundamental operations, difficulty to comprehend mathematical problems both numerical and word problems, and difficulty in dealing fraction. While in less mastered learning competencies in mathematics, the researchers found out that some topics in their respective subjects are not mastered by the learners like operations on rational numbers, factoring, analysis and problem solving, trigonometric identities, and statistical software. And for the less mastered skills in mathematics, the researcher found out that the skills that need to be mastered by learners in mathematics are more on numeracy skills specifically problem-solving skills, numerical ability, and data analysis skill.

Generally, these are the perceived learning difficulties of the teachers in their learners on their respective subjects. These findings are vital and an initial step to provide solutions to the educational crisis within the school and the division as well. These could contribute for the development of the new school program and framework. This is an eye opener for the stakeholders and not just for educators of the school that they should be more responsible for the learning outcomes of the learners. These findings are the bases of what would be the actions of the teachers and school head to address the perceived learning difficulties of their learners. These findings could be considered for the development and enhancement of some school programs for the development of the learners. These findings can be the bases for the modification of the learning competencies of mathematics for each grade level.

The findings of this study have some possible good impacts to the decisions and actions of the school head and most especially the mathematics teachers on how they will address these problems within the learners. Nonetheless, the results of this study must be interpreted with caution and several limitations should be borne in mind. There are two major limitations in this study that could be addressed in future research. First, the study had just focused on perceptions of few teachers within one school. Although this school is a big school in the division of Marikina City but it would be better if more participants, including the learners from other schools within the division could participate in this study

to gather more data. Second is the process of gathering the data from the participants where the survey questionnaire were sent through the messenger with the use of the google form. There was no face-to-face interview done in gathering the data for all teachers during the process of data collection were in vacation. So, the researcher suggests that these limitations and weaknesses should be considered by future researchers if they wish to conduct the same study.

Recommendations

Overall, there is a need for continued research on identifying some factors that causes these perceived learning difficulties of the learners in mathematics that affect their academic performance, as this has important implications on the learner`s ability that could be the bases of the actions of school head and mathematics teachers to address the poor performances of the learners not just in Mathematics but in all subject areas. Factors causing the learning difficulties of the learners should be identified if it is a family factor, system factor, leadership factor, teacher`s factor, and etc. These factors that affect the learner`s ability must be identified and confirmed to make an appropriate solution and immediate actions to the identified mathematical learning difficulties of the learners in this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, some ethical considerations were observed. The researcher had sought permission from the school head and Mathematics department head. An informed consent was also obtained from the participants for their awareness of the purpose, procedures, risks, benefits of the study together with their rights to withdraw anytime they want. The names and the responses of the respondents were kept confidential. For confidentiality of the name of the school a pseudonym was used which is Marikit Normal School.

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REFERENCES

Decena, R. (2021). Enhancement of Mathematics Competency through Independent/Cooperative Learning (ICL). *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational*

- Perspectives. Vol. 8 No.1, 114-127. Retrieved from <https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph>
- Fauzi, et al (2023). Complex Thinking: How are Students' Mathematical Problem-Solving Skills in Elementary School?. *Bulletin of Science Education* 3(3):228. [https:// DOI:10.51278/bse.v3i3.916](https://doi.org/10.51278/bse.v3i3.916). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Hodaňová, H. & Nocar, D. (2016). Mathematics Importance in Our Life. 10th annual International Technology, Education and Development. [https:// DOI: 10.21125/inted.2016.0172](https://doi.org/10.21125/inted.2016.0172). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Jade, S. & Oco, R. (2023). Students' Mathematical Skills and Performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, Volume 6, Issue 2, pp. 328-332, 2023. Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Kavitha, M. & Saravanakumar, AR. (2014). Effect of Performance in Basic Mathematical Operations Among Rural Upper Primary Children. *International Journal of Scientific Research* 3(11):122. Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Khanal, B. (2022). Approaches for Enhancing Mathematics Learning of Students with Learning Difficulties. *The Educator Journal* 10(1):88-92. [https:// DOI:10.3126/tej.v10i1.46731](https://doi.org/10.3126/tej.v10i1.46731). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Lacson, E. & Jaminal, J. (2024). Utilization of Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) to Enhance Least Mastered Mathematics Competencies. [https:// DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.28809.25444](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28809.25444). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Laña, G. (2023). Least Learned Competencies in Mathematics 8: Basis in Crafting Strategic Intervention Materials. *Journal of Research and Investigation in Education*. Volume 1, No. 3. <https://doi.org/10.37034/residu.v1i3.158>
- Magsambol, B. (2024, February 8). Why Filipino students performed poorly in global learning assessments. *Rappler*. Retrieved from <https://www.rappler.com>
- Melisa, M. & Utami, N. (2023). Students' Mathematical Literacy in solving Problems System of Equation of Three Variables. *Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika (Jupitek)* 6(1):42-48. [https:// DOI:10.51278/bse.v3i3.916](https://doi.org/10.51278/bse.v3i3.916). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Mitumba, H. & Chirwa, G. (2024). Experiences of Learners with Mathematics Learning Difficulties in Regular Classrooms in Malawian Secondary Schools. *East African Journal of Education and Social Sciences* 4(6):120-126. [https:// DOI:10.46606/eajess2023v04i06.033](https://doi.org/10.46606/eajess2023v04i06.033). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Murillo, J. & Tan, R. (2022). Design, Development, and Validation of Humorous Instructional Videos for the Least Mastered Competencies in Mathematics. *American Journal of Educational Research* 10(12):654-662. [https:// DOI:10.12691/education-10-12-1](https://doi.org/10.12691/education-10-12-1). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Murtiyasa, B. & Lahtifa, A. (2023). Mathematics Learning Difficulties in Distance Learning. *JETL (Journal Of Education Teaching and Learning)* 8(1):51. [https:// DOI:10.26737/jetl.v8i1.3433](https://doi.org/10.26737/jetl.v8i1.3433). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Nicolas, A. (2019). *Thematic Analysis – A Guide with Examples*. Research Prospect. 2023 edition. Retrieved from <https://www.researchprospect.com>

- Rodin, A. (2023). One Mathematic(s) or Many? Foundations of Mathematics in Today's Mathematical Practice. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2301.08131>. Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Romorosa, et al (2023). Improving Students' Achievement of Learning Competencies in Mathematics through Micro-Lecture via ED Puzzle. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* Vol. 10(No. 4):120-133. Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Sainio, P. et al (2019). The Role of Learning Difficulties in Adolescents' Academic Emotions and Academic Achievement. *Journal of Learning Disabilities* 52(4):002221941984156. [https:// DOI:10.1177/0022219419841567](https://doi.org/10.1177/0022219419841567). Retrieved from [http:// www.researchgate.net](http://www.researchgate.net)
- Tiedeman, S. (2019). The Impact of Early Math and Numeracy Skills on Academic Achievement in Elementary School.
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) (2017, forthcoming). "More Than One-Half of Children and Adolescents Are Not Learning Worldwide". Montreal: UNESCO Institute for Statistics.